

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

A stylistic-critical discourse analysis of persuasive strategies in King Abdullah II's Speeches

Asmaa Saffah Kareem *

Thi-Qar Education Directorate, Iraq.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 21(02), 1486–1498

Publication history: Received on 07 January 2024; revised on 18 February 2024; accepted on 20 February 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.21.2.0539>

Abstract

This study looks at the influence procedures or persuasive strategies utilized by King Abdullah II of Jordan provided for the UN, European Parliament, Association of Islamic Participation, and Bedouin Association somewhere in the range of 2007 and 2021. Intertextuality, Imagination and Illustration, References, and Diversion were utilized in the review to investigate how the King involved these persuasive methods in his discussions. The speeches are additionally being broken down utilizing Fairclough's discourse investigation approach. King Abdullah II utilized representations, references, aversion, and intertextuality, as indicated by the review. He featured reality as it is utilizing an inventive strategy. Furthermore, he utilizes intertextuality to convince the world local area of his point of view. The King, then again, stays away from unoriginality in his comments by utilizing nonpartisan pronouns like "we," "our," "your," and "you." It takes a look at the purposeful utilization of language to stimulate sentiments, support convictions, and make a positive view of the speaker or political faction. Then Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) offers a hypothetical system to take a look at the power the social and political variables have underlined in political discourse. It shows the way that language can be utilized to keep up with control, bar specific gatherings from society, or reinforcing existing power structures. Stylistics and CDA are utilized in this review to give a comprehensive understanding with complex perception of the influence (or persuasion) strategies employed in political discourse.

Keywords: Persuasive; Strategies; Political Discourse; Stylistic-CDA

1. Introduction

Political communication, legislative choices, influencing public opinion and directing society advancement, are essential fields that depend on discourse as a powerful weapon for persuasion. In the domain of politics, discourse has many characteristics like rhetorical tactics, contextual nuances and the complex interplay of linguistic choices (Wodak, et al, 2016: 29). By using a Stylistic-Critical Discourse Analysis (Stylistic-CDA) methodology to analyze the complex web of persuasion tactics used by political players, this study probes the core of this linguistic talent. A thorough lens through which we examine the complex nature of political persuasion is provided by the combination of stylistics and critical discourse analysis. Stylistics is a branch of linguistics that examines the aesthetic and expressive aspects of language use by examining the role that vocabulary, grammar, metaphor, and tone choices play in the creation of meaning. The Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) method, on the other hand, reveals the underlying ideologies, power structures, and social structures that both shape and are shaped by language in use. Combining both techniques in one approach "Stylistic-CDA" provides a comprehensive understanding of the persuasive strategies in political discourse as well as illuminating the socio-political settings of these strategies to a large extent.

This study aims at discovering, classifying, and assessing the techniques of persuasion used in political discourse. We aim to identify the nuanced language strategies used by politicians to manipulate public opinion and spark social change

* Corresponding author: Asmaa Saffah Kareem; Email: dr.asmaakareem@gmail.com

through the analysis of a variety of texts, including campaign speeches, policy statements, media interviews, and social media posts. The study also aims to clarify the ways in which prevailing ideologies, power structures, and social norms are reflected, reinforced, or challenged by these persuasive methods. The political scene of today is characterized by a growing reliance on different media outlets for message dissemination (van Leeuwen, 2008: 25). Thus, this study is going to recognize the dynamic nature of political discourse including both conventional and digital communication channels. Since political agents use memes, soundbites, and social media to their benefits, linguists increasingly face a complex analysis that demand necessarily a detailed grasp of persuasion resulted from the interaction of these various modalities.

2. Importance of Political Discourse Analysis

The analysis of political discourse is of utmost importance because of its essential role in impacting the dynamics of democratic societies, influencing policy choices and forming public opinions. This area of research focuses on analyzing how political actors utilize language, rhetoric, and communicative techniques to spread their messages, interact with the public, and further declare their own agendas. We can better understand the significance of political discourse analysis and its effects on various facets of society and governance by exploring its significance (Chilton, 2004: 56).

Political discourse is a major source of information for people to learn about the stances, ideologies, and proposed policies of political candidates and parties. This promotes informed citizenship and democratic participation. Analyzing political discourse enables people to participate more actively in democratic processes and make informed decisions during elections. Analyzing the linguistic strategies utilized in political communication can lead people to evaluate the purposes, legitimacy, and expected outcomes of various political messages. These strategies include:

2.1. Formation of Public Opinion

The wording and context of political messaging greatly influence how the public feels about important topics. Discourse analysis reveals how politicians carefully assemble narratives, make emotional appeals, and frame discussions to affect how the general public perceives and reacts to certain issues. This understanding is crucial for comprehending how public opinion is shaped and how it may influence people's attitudes.

2.1.1. Policies Development and Implementation

Political discourse plays a role in the policies creation and execution. Discourse analysis reveals the arguments made against or in favour of a given policy, shedding light on the variables influencing policy choices. Policymakers can learn from this information about effective communication tactics for the key stakeholders and general public.

2.1.2. Accountability and Transparency

A thorough analysis of political discourse can point out inconsistencies, discrepancies, or manipulative strategies utilized by political actors. The general public and analysts can hold politicians accountable for their remarks and actions by closely examining the language and terminology used. This encourages accountability and cultivates a climate of responsible communication in politics. Political discourse reflects and supports values, cultural norms, and ideologies, according to cultural and ideological insights. Linguistic and rhetorical choices of political communication can be studied to reveal underlying power relationships, ideologies and implicit prejudices. Having this knowledge is dependent in understanding how language supports or undermines prevailing cultural narratives (Wilson, 2015: 788).

2.2. The Effective Interplay of Stylistics and Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA)

The combination of stylistics and critical discourse analysis (CDA) produces a strong analytical framework which enables researchers to delve deeply into the subtleties of language use within political discourse and also reveal the underlying power dynamics and socio-political implications (van Dijk, 2015: 57) . This interplay improves our comprehension of how language works as a persuasion tool as well as a reflection of larger social processes. Some specifics of this harmony are examined below.

2.2.1. Stylistics

This language study places a strong emphasis on language's aesthetic and expressive qualities. The key component of this process is to analyze how linguistic choices, such as vocabulary, grammar, metaphor, tone, and style, contribute to the process of making meaning and elicit particular emotional reactions. Stylistic analysis can find language usage patterns that make political discourse more compelling. Examining the use of vivid metaphors or emotive language, for

instance, might show how the audience is captivated to arouse specific emotions through purposefully using these linguistic strategies (Simpson, P. (2014: 78).

2.2.2. Using Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) to explore Power and Ideology

Critical discourse analysis explores the complex interrelatedness between language, power, and social systems. Its goal is to expose covert ideologies, hegemonic narratives, and the ways in which language reinforces or subverts power relations. It looks at how language can shape public perceptions and support or challenge prevailing beliefs. The crucial role of applying critical discourse analysis to political discourse is to analyze how language decisions reflect and support political beliefs, marginalization, and socioeconomic inequities (van Dijk, 2015: 69).

2.2.3. Enhanced Understanding through Fusion

The fusion of stylistics and CDA enhances our analysis by giving us a thorough understanding of political discourse. The CDA sheds light on the socio-political implications and effects of these strategies, whereas stylistics supports our understanding of the artistry and persuasive strategies inherent in language. The interaction enables us to uncover deeper layers of meaning by going beyond superficial studies and illuminating how linguistic techniques help achieve persuasive goals and support or impair societal power structures (Machin, 2016: 114)

2.3. Political Persuasion

Politicians can, persuade, influence, or move people or organizations to embrace a given political situation, support a particular policy, or take certain actions by using rhetoric and communication strategies. It is an essential component of political communication to influence public opinion, energize the electorate, and advance policy objectives. Below are some important specifics about political persuasion (Hogan, 2007: 38).

2.3.1. Communication Strategies

Political players, such as parties, politicians, interest groups, or governments, make planned and deliberate efforts to create communication messages that appeal to their target audience. These messages try to evoke a desired response or action by crafting them carefully to appeal to values, beliefs and emotions (Pelclova, 2018: 27)

2.3.2. Rhetorical Strategies

A variety of rhetorical strategies, including engaging narratives, , logical justifications, emotive appeals, and vivid metaphors, are frequently used in political discourse to persuade audiences. Rhetoric helps make a message more powerful and long-remembered by establishing a link between the speaker and the listener (Musolff, 2016: 96).

2.3.3. Emotional appeals

The key component in political persuasion are emotions. Strong emotional reactions such as hope, fear, wrath, or empathy are more likely to influence people and inspire them to take action. Thus, candidates frequently make emotional appeals in order to establish rapport and rally support (Perloff, 2003: 109).

2.3.4. Reliability and Trust

Reliability and trust must be established in order to make persuasion successful. Political actors' messages must be viewed as trustworthy and genuine so as to be effective. A combination of prior behavior, character traits, and persistent messaging are required in building trust (Pattison, 2014: 50).

2.3.5. Targeting Specific Audiences

Political persuasion is based on interests, opinions and demographics and is customized to specific audiences. Different groups may react differently to different messages, requiring the need for communicators to adjust their tactics accordingly (Loundslager, 2012: 18).

3. Literature Review

The critical work of Fairclough (1992) identifies the complex interrelationship between language and social change, particularly within the discourse environment. He offers the idea of "critical discourse analysis" (CDA) for the purpose of identifying the ways in which language both reflects and contributes to societal transformations. Fairclough placed focus on ideologies, power dynamics, and discourse structures to provide a conceptual framework for a critical

examination of political speech's persuasive tactics. His framework offers perceptive comprehension of how political actors employ language to promote social change and sway public opinion.

The work of Van Dijk (2015) examines the notion of ideology across numerous fields and provides a thorough framework to comprehend how language communicate and manipulate ideologies. His interdisciplinary approach emphasizes the interaction between ideology's cognitive, social, and discourse components. Researchers can use this work as a useful starting point for examining the ideological foundations of persuasion tactics in political discourse and can learn how prevailing ideas can be supported or contradicted through linguistic choices.

Chilton's book (2004) provides a detailed manual for analyzing political discourse which combines theoretical understanding with real-world applications. Chilton gives academics the tools they need to find persuasive tactics in political communication by proposing crucial terms like "cognitive framing" and "manipulation". His method creates a link between theory and practice, making it a crucial tool for academics looking to analyze the persuasive strategies used by politicians.

This edited collection together with essays from several academics working in the field of critical discourse analysis (CDA), provide a variety of methodological viewpoints for examining conversations (Wodak, 2015: 44) . [6] The book provides a thorough manual for performing critical discourse analysis with chapters on both textual and contextual analysis. This volume gives numerous techniques that can help academics choose the best resources to illustrate ideological bases and persuasion tactics in political contest.

Partington (2018: 411) introduced a paper which emphasizes the mutually beneficial link between corpora and discourse analysis, and highlights the function of corpora in revealing linguistic patterns. This study is important for stylistic-CDA scholars because it shows how corpus linguistics may improve the identification and analysis of linguistic aspects, assisting in the explore of the persuasion tactics in political discourse.

Simpson (2014: 63) also gives a thorough introduction to stylistics which offers insights into numerous linguistic strategies used in language use. This tool provides a basis for understanding how linguistic decisions influence persuasion tactics for researchers using a stylistic-CDA approach, assisting in the analysis of the aesthetic and expressive components of political discourse.

In Kress & van Leeuwen (2021: 98) the study of metaphors in speech focuses on how they are used to shape and spread ideologies. This book is important for researchers who consider metaphors in political speech because it offers techniques used to identify the ideological attribute of metaphorical language.

Machin (2016: 101) provided the introduction to multimodal analysis with insights into the interaction of many modes of communication, such as language, images, and other visual components. This tool enables academics to analyze persuasive methods beyond linguistic choices, taking into account the visual and environmental components of political discourse, since political communication increasingly embodies multimodal forms.

4. Methodology

This segment precisely represents the methods utilized in this study.

4.1. Data Collection

The corpus of this study is made up of seven speeches made by King Abdullah II at provincial and worldwide culminations, including the Overall Get together of the Unified Countries, the European Parliament, the Islamic Nations Participation, and the Bedouin Association somewhere in the range of 2007 and 2021. These speeches were assembled from Lord Abdullah's genuine site. The deciding element in the choice of these speeches shows their importance to the objectives of the study as they stress on harmony and the compelled need for Israeli-Palestinian compromise. In this manner, these political discourses could accomplish the objectives of the ongoing review, which was to clarify the harmony philosophy remembered for Lord Abdullah II's discussions. The Jordanian Imperial Court employs mediators and interpreters to make an interpretation of speeches from English into Arabic (Machin & Mayr, (2023: 36).

4.2. Data Analysis

The ongoing review leads to examine the corpus chosen in full concentration to recognize tokens, errors, the recurrence of the most often happening terms, the recurrence of the expression "harmony," and the collocations of "harmony" in the corpus. Furthermore, the review utilizes text investigation, rambling practices, and social practices — the three CDA

aspects characterized by Fairclough — as its calculated system. The concentration likewise utilizes to feature the power elements, political setting, and verifiable foundation of Lord's speeches that contain "harmony" (Baker, et al, 2013: 81).

5. Results and Discussion

This part consists of two sections. The first will do a measurable examination of the corpus by giving information on grammatical errors, tokens, the recurrence of the most often happening words, "harmony," and the collocation of "harmony" in the corpus. The second will analyze the King Abdulla's II speeches considering the three parts of CDA (Fairclough, 1992) and the persuasive strategies recommended by Obeng (Obeng, 1997).

5.1. Statistical Information

The chosen corpus is assessed by utilizing Wordsmith8. The analysis can include the 'tokens' and 'types' in the picked corpus due to the devices presented by Wordsmith8. The little units known as 'tokens' can be found in the corpus paying little attention to the number of their occurrences. Conversely, 'type' alludes to the particular terms that are repeated across the corpus. The review will show the proportion of 'token' and 'type' to notice the lexical thickness of the text highlights.

5.1.1. English Source Text (S. T.) versus Arabic Target Text (T. T.)

In this part, the analysis differentiates the spans of the English (S. T. corpus) and Arabic (T. T. corpus) corpora. Wordsmith8 is used as shown in Table1 and 2 below.

Table 1 Data from the English corpus (WS8)

W	File		N	1
Wordlist	<u>E</u> dit			Overall
	<u>V</u> iew			
	<u>C</u> ompute			
	<u>S</u> etting			
	<u>W</u> indows			
	<u>H</u> elp	Text file		
		File size		2,00,000
		Tokens	(running words) in	37,648
		Tokens	Used for word list	37.421
		Sum of	entries	37,648
		Types	(distinct type/token standard std. dev. Words) ratio	3,562
			TTR	24.34
		STTR		55.89
		STTR		43.62
		mean	Basis word length	2
		Word	Length	1.67
		std. dev	5.72	
	Entences		2.445	
	Mean (in words)		20.93	

Table 2 Data from the Arabic corpus (WS8).

W	File		N	1	
Wordlist	<u>E</u> dit				Overall
	<u>V</u> iew				
	<u>C</u> ompute				
	<u>S</u> etting				
	<u>W</u> indows				
	<u>H</u> elp	Text file			
		File size			2,00,000
		Tokens	(running words) in		17,860
		Tokens	Used for word list		37.423
		Sum of	entries		31,189
		Types	(distinct type/token standard std. dev. Words) ratio		5,912
					44.66
			TTR		76.28
		STTR			29.64
		STTR			2,000
		mean	Basis word length		4.13
	Word	Length	std. dev	1.91	
	Entences			862	
	Mean (in words)			12.82	

5.1.2. Types and Tokens in the Study Corpus

The size of the corpus for both English and Arabic is shown in the tables above. The Arabic corpus has 31,189 tokens, contrasted with 37,648 tokens in the English corpus. This disparity exhibits that the Arabic corpus is more modest than the English one. 3,562 words make up the sort (various words), whereas 5,912 words make up the Arabic one of the same sort. The distinction in the quantity of types recommends that Arabic has a more noteworthy number of remarkable terms because of the lexical thickness of Arabic, which is proper for the Arabic language. The Arabic word ", " which can be deciphered as "will we drive you to acknowledge it," can be converted into various English words. The English type/token proportion shows that it is 24.34, whereas in the Arabic corpus it is 44.66. This is likewise apparent in the Normalized TTR, which is 55.89 for the English corpus and 76.28 for the Arabic one.

Table 3 Types and tokens in the English and Arabic corpora

Criterion	English Corpus	Arabic Corpus
Tokens	29.812	26.331
Types	4.612	7.751
Type/Tokens Ratio	15.66	39.61
Standardized TTR (%)	45.98	71.91

Figure 1 Types and tokens in the English and Arabic corpora

5.1.3. Frequency Analysis

The most often happening words in the text are followed through recurrence examination. It subsequently shows the text's more and more uncommon words. To achieve the objective of this review, the specialist ordered a rundown of words that showed up much of the time in both English and Arabic texts. Furthermore, Table 3 shows the recurrence of "harmony" in King Abdullah II's discourses.

Table 4 The most well-known words in the English and Arabic corpora

WWordlist				WWordlist							
Edit	View	Compute	Setting	windows	help	Edit	View	Compute	Setting	windows	help
N			Words	Freq.		N			Words	Freq.	
1			The	2,665		1			أنا	432	
2			A	567		2			التي	956	
3			On	244		3			الله	7584	
4			Of	728		4			على	326	
5			For	365		5			السلام	157	
6			To	672		6			إن	958	
7			That	345		7			عن	124	
8			It	254		8			كل	32	
9			This	318		9			لا	25	
10			We	455		10			#	45	

The English corpus contains 26 much of the time happening terms, 26 of which are linguistic (capability) and content words. The words "the" and "a", relational words like "on", "of", "for" and "to", pronouns like "that", "it", "this", and "we", and conjunctions like "and" are among them. On the opposite side, the Arabic wordlist incorporates specific terms, such as the content words "في", "من", "كل", "على". Shut words are capability words, which are critical in deciding the association between two linguistic components and they are used to convey tenses and linguistic connections. In view

of its syntactic position, each functional word has an extraordinary importance to exhibit that this importance of the capability word is essential to understand sentences. Useful terms are bound to contain capability words than content words.

Capability terms ought to be completely perceived by interpreters. The false utilization of capability words brings about friendly and political issues that cannot be endured by countries. While making an interpretation of one language into another, the interpreter ought to consider capability terms in light of the fact that different perspectives can be prompted.

5.2. Persuasive Strategies

The subsequent segment looks at a couple of King Abdullah II's discourses to decide the influence (persuasive) strategies he utilized to introduce his vision of harmony. As indicated by Obeng, persuasive strategies incorporate inventiveness, intertextuality, circumvention, inference, and allegory. The three phases will likewise be utilized to assess the previously mentioned persuasive strategies.

5.2.1. Creativity and Metaphors

In spite of the fact that imagination and analogy are separate strategies, they are expected to advance innovative correspondence. Basically, we can address them at the same time to convey the explorations plainly. Then, starting with one calculated space then onto the next, a semantic planning is vital for illustrations, and this is regularly achieved utilizing peculiar or unusual language. Government officials use analogies to differentiate between two thoughts.

Imagination is the ability of using language to deliver ideas that go further the speaker's intention. In legislative issues, government officials depend vigorously on imagination as a point of support in convincing people to help their strategies and target claims that discourse is a belief system. Accordingly, the speaker's most urgent instrument for convincing the crowd of his thoughts is creativity. By analyzing King Abdullah II's assertions, it can be perceived that the Ruler's way to deal with the Middle Eastern circumstance is innovative. Ruler Abdullah II talked at the Brookings Foundation Meeting in 2021 showing his creativity by utilizing the accompanying terms.

Example 1: *We have found, notwithstanding, that the diligent shamefulness in our space will keep on holding every one of us back. Without harmony, thriving in the Middle East and its advantages for the whole globe can't appear.*

In this section, the Ruler underlines the meaning of settling the Palestine struggle in the Middle East. [18] The Middle East's improvement will be impeded by the shortfall of an answer, which will significantly affect the rest of the world. The Ruler requires a restart of the Palestinian-Israeli clash's calmness cycle. The expression utilized here shows King Abdullah's technique of stressing the worth of harmony for the progression of the region and the whole world. The Middle Eastern emergency center will think well about the district's advancement by prohibiting the fundamental foundations of brutality

This fine art creatively illustrates Ruler Abdullah's objective of further developing Palestinian-Israeli harmony talks. This view underlines how Israelis and Palestinians are experiencing the same thing as they are both in danger of treacheries. Moreover, the Ruler inventively depicts Middle Eastern life as "flourishing [...] can't work out as expected without harmony". King discusses making the harmony cycle crucial for the abundance and development of the region. 'We will be helpless against dangers both locally and globally without harmony'.

Example 2: *An opportunity exists to expand on late useful turns of events. Our childhood should be carried more like a future that has long appeared to be tantalizingly too far, and we want to revamp confidence in the plausibility of harmony.*

Additionally, the Ruler portrays the cycle of harmony nearby to be continuous. He puts areas of strength on getting back harmony request to incite the district's turn of events and move for future. Moreover, the Ruler's vision underlines the way in which urgent harmony is directed to the concurrence of people in the future. The connection among dismal and ideal pictures interfaces the social ways of Israelis' and Palestinians' behavior since they share a similar nation and whose the state of affairs threatens them. Here, the Lord urges correspondence between the communities to determine their disparities and impede collapse. The two players are reminded that they are in danger by the negative picture, whereas the hopeful picture, including a superior future for people, features the advantages of harmony.

Example 3: *A decade after the association's origin, Jordan joined. As a functioning part state making progress toward world harmony and economical turn of events, we play acknowledged our part.*

Ruler Abdullah II reaffirms Jordan's obligation to propel worldwide harmony and manageable advancement as a functioning member from the UN. In this sense, the Ruler keenly helps the world to remember Jordan's significance in any future dealings for settling the Middle Eastern disputes. In addition, he emphasizes the role of Jordan in the commitment to the overall work to progress worldwide manageable turn of events.

Example 4: *Furthermore, we can't end this emergency without attempting to safeguard Jerusalem as a city of harmony and solidarity for all of mankind. I have a particular commitment as the Hashemite Caretaker to safeguard the sacred spots of Islam and Christianity in Jerusalem, however we are liable for the Blessed City.*

In model 3, the Ruler perceives Jordan's commitment to settling Middle Eastern struggles, particularly the Israeli-Palestinian clash. Here, the Ruler alludes to the global local area as "we" to underscore the unoriginality of his location with respect to Jerusalem and his objective of persuading the world to track down a calm answer for the Palestinian-Israeli clash. Jerusalem is creatively depicted in the Ruler's talk as 'a spot where each of the three religions might exist together'. Thus, Jerusalem should be seen as the city of harmony as opposed to struggle. Then again, the King additionally reminds everybody that Jordan is responsible for the sacred destinations in Jerusalem that are both Christian and Islamic. He suggests that any answer for the Palestinian Israelis ought to be concurred with Jordan because Jordan is the watchman of the holy spots of Islam and Christianity in Jerusalem,

Example 5: *"In Bethany, Jordan, the shocking Holy person Garabed Armenian Missional Church remains with satisfaction. Jesus Christ's baptismal site lies past the Jordan; harmony arrive.*

When the King shows how the Missional Church has a rich legacy in Jordan, he implies Jordan's celebrated strict past. It is arranged where Jesus, harmony arrive, was submerged in the Jordan Stream. This reference recommends that conjunction plays had a huge impact in Jordanian history. [19] Furthermore, the Ruler utilizes the Islamic greeting "harmony arrive" to convey what Muslims accept when they utter or hear the name of Jesus, harmony arrive. In addition, this term infers that it is essential to our Islamic convictions to regard for Jesus and Christians.

5.2.2. Periphrasis

The ambiguous way to deal with or convey something nasty or disgusting is by antipathy. Legislators frequently utilize bypass to try not to be excessively barefaced and conceal any hint of failure. Moreover, they utilize antipathy to counter the contentions of their adversaries. All the more essentially considerable utilization of diversion can assist lawmakers to achieve their targets or objectives and to scatter fake data about their opponents. In such manners, legislators use elusion, misrepresentation and poetic overstatement as their essential techniques to scatter any harming data about their objectives.

King Abdullah II talked at many highest points and global get-togethers situations. Nevertheless, the Ruler need to emphasize particular issues in his location whereas most of his essential worries are placed on the basic issues in the Middle East:

- Israeli-Palestinian dispute.
- Upholding Palestinian rights is the responsibility of the international community.
- Renewing the peace process by the unbiased voice of America.
- Urging to unite the world community in resisting the threats.
- Jordan's role in promoting regional peace.

Table 5 below records the highest terms King Abdullah II uses most often: "Must" seems multiple times with a frequency of 98, the word "Palestinian" is referenced frequently with 78 times of occurrence, "Jerusalem" is referenced 65 times, "The Middle East" is referenced 30 times, "Palestinian-Israeli" is referenced 22 times, "should" is referenced 20 times, and "America" has the lowest reference with 10 times only.

Table 5 The seven speeches' most common words

Word	Part of Speech	Frequency
Must	Verb	98
Palestinian	Noun	78
Jerusalem	Noun	65
Middle East	Noun	30
Palestinian-Israeli	Noun	22
Should	Verb	20
America	Noun	10

Figure 2 The seven speeches' most common words

In his discussions, the Ruler mentions “I should” multiple times. This expression is significant in light of the fact that it distinguishes the principal objective of the discourse. The Lord upholds his objective of a quiet goal to the Israeli-Palestinian issue by utilizing the expression "must" in this sentence.

Example 6: *What’s more, today, I must tell the truth and concede that the risks have expanded because of continuous struggle, settlement development, and scorn for worldwide regulation.*

To prevent a heightening that would compromise the soundness of the locale and the whole globe settlement, the Lord asserts that the worldwide local area ought to collaborate to revive the harmony cycle among Palestinians and Israelis. In this way, there is a need for a quiet goal to the Israeli-Palestinian issue. It is crucial to comprehend from the expression "should" that the Ruler is eager for the existence of a careful harmony process between the Palestinians and Israelis. Then again, the expression "should" supports more noteworthy activity by the vital gatherings to determine the Middle East emergency. The Ruler needs to convince the crowd of his vision, consequently he utilizes the words "should and ought to" to convey what these expressions eventually allude as the understanding step.

Political pronouns are utilized to exhibit character, office and self-reference. As a representation, the objective pronouns "us" and "them" connect with the division of society into in- and out- gatherings. Ruler Abdullah II was exact in his selection of pronouns to underscore the message he wished to pass on. First and second singular pronouns are utilized by King Abdullah II more than third singular pronouns. The first and second pronouns empower the speaker to address the crowd explicitly and simplify his assertion to understand. By finding some kind of harmony, King Abdullah II can

amaze his crowd and make them focus on the message he needs to pass on. This equilibrium is regarding the Fairclough social practice aspect because it recommends that this discourse is a social practice instead of a phonetic one.

Example 7: *Jordan joined the UN decade after it was laid out. As a functioning part state taking a stab at world harmony and supportable turn of events, we play acknowledged our part.*

Table 6 records the recurrence of the subject pronouns involved in King Abdullah II's talks. It has been laid out that Ruler Abdullah II utilized the pronoun "we" several times more than other pronouns in his discussions. This recurrence makes the connection between the speaker and the crowd vital. The utilization of "we" certifies the discourse's authenticity and exhibits the fairness of all discourse parties. The second person pronoun "you" is utilized normally multiple times but not more than the first person "I," which is utilized 50 times, as shown in Table 6 below. The discourse's utilization of singular pronouns shows that the speaker needs to obtain the crowd's trust and understanding.

Ruler Abdullah II underlines Jordan's commitment to help out all global gatherings to achieve world harmony. He utilizes the pronouns "we" and "our" to demonstrate that he represents all Jordanians, and to upgrade the positive impression of the gathering to which he has a place.

Table 6 The subject pronoun King Abdullah II uses in his talks

Pronoun	Frequency
We	120
I	50
You	30

Figure 3 The subject pronoun King Abdullah II uses in his talks

Table 7 The use of possessive pronouns in King Abdullah's speeches

N.	Possessive Pronouns	Frequency
1.	Our	150
2.	Your	60
3.	My	40

Figure 4 The use of possessive pronouns in King Abdullah's speeches

6. Results

Table 8 Maximum Frequency in Seven Speeches

Maximum Frequency in seven speeches' most common words	In Verb 98
Maximum Frequency in seven speeches' most common words	In Noun 78
Maximum Frequency in Pronoun	(We)120
Maximum Frequency in Possessive Pronouns (Our)	(Our) 150

"We" is the most often utilized plural pronoun to adjust the Lord and his crowd, as indicated in Table 5, which is predictable with the previous discoveries. The Ruler, then again, tries not to be distant in that frame of mind by not involving objective pronouns to persuade the crowd of his vision of harmony in the Middle East.

Example 8: *In this way, there are two things that join us collectively here. Our obligation to these great many people, who have entrusted us with their desires and stresses, starts things out.*

In his comments to the European Parliament, King Abdullah II utilized the plural pronouns "we" and "our" referring to the members of the European Parliament as well as the speaker, himself. He uses "us" rather than "we" to lay out bunch investment as opposed to helping them to remember his power. He also utilizes the possessive pronoun "our" to advise them that helping to encourage expectation and alleviate the concerns of the evacuees and host countries is the aggregate commitment of Jordan and European countries.

7. Conclusion

The focal point of CDA, an interdisciplinary field, is to investigate political discourses and their social jobs. The review takes a look at how King Abdullah II utilized "harmony" in seven locations at culminations that were held globally, territorially, and locally somewhere in the range of 2007 and 2022. As indicated by the review's discoveries, much of the time he utilizes imagination to stress or focus the points he needs to raise. Moreover, Ruler Abdullah persuades the crowd of his vision by using intertextuality. As per the report, Ruler Abdullah II stresses Jordan's commitment to settling worldwide emergencies including the Israeli-Palestinian struggle. The utilization of persuasive strategies arises as a strong power that molds mentalities, coordinates choices, and influences the improvement of social orders in the complicated universe of political discourse.[20] This study utilized a Stylistic-Basic Discourse Examination (Stylistic-CDA) strategy to research and unravel the creativity and meaning of these persuasive strategies inside the setting of political correspondence. A few significant disclosures and outcomes have arisen in this review. Stylistics and Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) cooperate to make major areas of strength for examining the numerous features of influence strategies in political discourse. Consolidating stylistic examination has delivered an intensive comprehension of how political entertainers use language to make convincing stories, by uncovering the stylish choices and nuances of discourse, with the basic focal point of CDA, which uncovers hidden power elements and philosophical underpinnings.

The study has uncovered the intricate snare of persuasive strategies utilized by political communicators through the thorough examination of many political messages, including discourses, declarations, online entertainment posts, and meetings. We took a look at how illustrations are deliberately used to stimulate sentiments, how crowds answer expository gadgets, and how changes in tone and register imply changes in significance. These influence procedures, which were for some time concealed in etymological subtlety, are presently in plain view and are contemplated, exhibiting the way that they add to the making of political real factors.

References

- [1] Baker, P., Gabrielatos, C., & McEnery, T. (2013). *Discourse Analysis and Media Attitudes: The Representation of Islam in the British Press*. Cambridge University Press.
- [2] Chilton, P. (2004). *Analyzing Political Discourse: Theory and Practice*. Routledge.
- [3] Fairclough, N. (1992). *Discourse and Social Change*. Polity Press.
- [4] Hogan, Kevin. *The Psychology of Persuasion: How to Persuade Others to Your Way of Thinking*. USA: Pelican Publishing Company, 2007.
- [5] Kress, G., & van Leeuwen, T. (2021). *Multimodal Discourse: The Modes and Media of Contemporary Communication*. Arnold.
- [6] Loundslager, Michael W. (2012). *What We Can Learn About the Art of Persuasion from Candidate Abraham Lincoln: A Rhetorical Analysis of the Three Speeches That Propelled Him into The Presidency*. USA: university of Grundy.
- [7] Machin, D. (2016). *Introduction to Multimodal Analysis*. Routledge.
- [8] Machin, D., & Mayr, A. (2023). *How to Do Critical Discourse Analysis: A Multimodal Introduction*. Sage Publications.
- [9] Musolf, A. (2016). *Political Metaphor Analysis: Discourse and scenarios*. London: Bloomsbury.
- [10] Partington, A. (2018). Corpora and Discourse: A Most Congenial Relationship. *International Journal of Corpus Linguistics*, 9(3), 401-419.
- [11] Pattison, O. (2014). Outrage and Engage: A Story of Eminent Domani. *Journal of Legal Studies Education*, 31 (1), 55-88.
- [12] Pelclová, J., & Lu, W. (2018). *Persuasion in Public Discourse: Cognitive and Functional Perspectives*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins Publishing Company.
- [13] Perloff, R. M. (2003). *The Dynamics of Persuasion. Communication and Attitudes in the 21st Century*. Mahwah, N.J.: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- [14] Simpson, P. (2014). *Stylistics: A Resource Book for Students*. Routledge.
- [15] van Dijk, T. A. (2015). *Ideology: A Multidisciplinary Approach*. Sage Publications.
- [16] van Leeuwen, T. (2008). *Discourse and Practice: New Tools for Critical Discourse Analysis*. Oxford University Press.
- [17] Wilson, J. (2015). 'Political Discourse'. In D. Schiffrin, D. Tannen, & H. E. Hamilton (Eds.), *The Handbook of Discourse Analysis* (2nd ed.) (pp. 775–794). UK: John Wiley & Sons
- [18] Wodak, R., & Meyer, M. (2016). *Critical Discourse Analysis: History, Agenda, Theory, and Methodology*. In R. Wodak & M. Meyer (Eds.), *Methods of Critical Discourse Analysis* (3rd ed., pp. 1-32). Sage Publications.
- [19] Wodak, R., & Meyer, M. (Eds.). (2015). *Methods of Critical Discourse Analysis* (2nd ed.). Sage Publications.